

Implementations of Real-Time System Identification Using Recursive Techniques

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Abstract:

Recursive identification techniques offer the ability to compute the transfer function of a system in real-time. This mathematical representation of a system may be used for various tasks such as health monitoring and feedback control. This paper presents the mathematical development of the Fast Transversal filter. It follows reference [1], but adds to it by the introduction of a forgetting factor to accommodate changes in the plant. The FTF's ability to track plant changes in real time offers applications in adaptive feedback control and adaptive fault detection. An example of the use of the FTF in feedback control is presented for a simple plant. Also, it is demonstrated that the FTF may be used to estimate a mathematical model of a Flight Control Computer for command signals during the Autoland phase. The example shown in this paper is for a B737 Autolander.

1.) Mathematical Development:

This section examines two recursive system identification techniques and their derivation with a forgetting factor. The forgetting factor is incorporated into each technique and results are shown to illustrate the advantage of using an online identification scheme that discounts past input-output measurements in favor of recent measurements. The derivations of recursive least squares and the fast transversal filter are outlined with a forgetting factor. The basic derivation is taken from reference [1] and follows the notation with the addition of the forgetting factor.

Consider the linear difference model shown in Eq. (1)

$$y(k) + \sum_{i=1}^p \bar{Y}_i^{(2)} y(k-i) = \sum_{i=1}^p \bar{Y}_i^{(1)} u(k-i) + Du(k) \quad (1)$$

Here, p is the system order, u is the input, and y is the output. This may be written in compact notation as

$$y(k) = \sum_{i=1}^p \bar{Y}_i v(k-i) + Du(k) \quad v = \begin{bmatrix} y \\ u \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\bar{Y}_i = \begin{bmatrix} -\bar{Y}_i^{(2)} & \bar{Y}_i^{(1)} \end{bmatrix}$$

Equation (1) may be written in vector form as shown in Eq. (2)

$$y(k) = \bar{Y} v_p(k-1) \quad v_p(k-1) = \begin{bmatrix} u(k) \\ v(k-1) \\ \vdots \\ v(k-p) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\bar{Y} = [D \quad \bar{Y}_1 \quad \dots \quad \bar{Y}_p] \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) is for time step k . If one starts at time step 0 and stack up the equations for all time steps 0 through k , one obtains Eq. (3).

$$\phi(k) = \bar{Y} V_p(k-1)$$

$$\phi(k) = [y(0) \quad y(1) \quad y(2) \quad \dots \quad y(p) \quad \dots \quad y(k)] \quad (3)$$

$$V_p(k-1) = \begin{bmatrix} u(0) & u(1) & u(2) & \dots & u(p) & \dots & u(k) \\ & v(0) & v(1) & \dots & v(p-1) & \dots & v(k-1) \\ & & v(0) & \dots & v(p-2) & \dots & v(k-2) \\ & & & \ddots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ & & & & & v(0) & \dots & v(k-p) \end{bmatrix}$$

Equation (3) is for time steps 0 through k . At time step $k+1$, a new column of input-output data is added as shown in Eq. (4), which is valid from time step 0 to time step $k+1$.

$$[\phi(k) \quad y(k+1)] = \bar{Y} [V_p(k-1) \quad v_p(k)] \quad (4)$$

In Eq. (4) all data measurements are given equal weight. However, it is desired to discount past measurements in favor of current measurements. In order to accomplish this, a forgetting factor is introduced as shown.

$$[\phi(k)\sqrt{\lambda} \quad y(k+1)] = \bar{Y} [V_p(k-1)\sqrt{\lambda} \quad v_p(k)]$$

Which may be written as

$$\phi(k+1) = \bar{Y} V_p(k)$$

Here the forgetting factor λ is introduced without altering the equality. The value of λ is chosen between 0 and 1 with 0 discounting all measurements before time $k+1$ and 1 counting as equal all measurements between time steps 0 and $k+1$. Typically in applications λ is chosen around 0.97, however experience must be relied upon to obtain the best results for each application.

The batch least squares solution of Eq. (4) is given in Eq. (5) along with the definition of the inverse of the data correlation matrix.

$$\bar{Y}(k+1) = \phi(k+1) V_p^T(k) P_p(k)$$

$$P_p(k) = [V_p(k) \quad V_p^T(k)]^{-1} \quad (5)$$

In order to derive a recursive relationship for the parameters of the difference equation, a recursive relationship is first developed for the inverse of the data correlation matrix $P_p(k)$ that includes the forgetting factor λ .

$$P_p(k) = \left[\begin{bmatrix} V_p(k-1)\sqrt{\lambda} & v_p(k) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} V_p^T(k-1)\sqrt{\lambda} \\ v_p^T(k) \end{bmatrix} \right]^{-1}$$

$$= [P_p^{-1}(k-1)\lambda \quad v_p(k)v_p^T(k)]^{-1}$$

Application of the matrix inverse lemma and some algebraic manipulations results in a weighted recursive relationship for the updating of $P_p(k)$ using the current data measurements. Here the past input-output measurements

contribute less to the computation of $P_p(k)$ than do the current data measurements.

$$P_p(k) = P_p(k-1) \left\{ I - \frac{v_p(k)v_p^T(k)P_p(k-1)}{\lambda + v_p^T(k)P_p(k-1)v_p(k)} \right\} / \lambda \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) may be used in conjunction with Eq. (5) to form a recursive update equation for the difference equation parameters. After some algebraic manipulations as shown in Ref [1], equation (7) results.

$$\hat{Y}(k+1) = \hat{Y}(k) + \left\{ y(k+1) - \hat{Y}(k)v_p(k) \right\} \frac{v_p^T(k)P_p(k-1)}{\lambda + v_p^T(k)P_p(k-1)v_p(k)} \quad (7)$$

Equations (6) and (7) form the Recursive Least-Squares (RLS) filter with the forgetting factor. The complete algorithm is shown in the equations below. At each time step the computations are performed.

$$G_p(k) = \frac{v_p^T(k)P_p(k-1)}{\lambda + v_p^T(k)P_p(k-1)v_p(k)}$$

$$\hat{y}(k+1) = \hat{Y}(k)v_p(k)$$

$$P_p(k) = P_p(k-1) \{ I - v_p(k)G_p(k) \} / \lambda$$

$$\hat{Y}(k+1) = \hat{Y}(k) + \{ y(k+1) - \hat{y}(k+1) \} G_p(k)$$

It is instructive to examine the error in the RLS estimates when a forgetting factor is used. Consider the estimates of the system output before the update and after the update as shown in Eq. (8) respectively.

$$e_p^-(k+1) = y(k+1) - \hat{Y}(k)v_p(k)$$

$$e_p^+(k+1) = y(k+1) - \hat{Y}(k+1)v_p(k) \quad (8)$$

The first equation is the error before an update and the second equation is the error after the update. These two equations can be combined to express the relationship between the two using the equation for the RLS gain vector as shown in Eq. (9).

$$e_p^+(k+1) = \frac{\lambda e_p^-(k+1)}{\lambda + v_p^T(k)P_p(k-1)v_p(k)} \quad (9)$$

This equation shows that after updating, the estimation error is smaller as one would expect. Also, the forgetting factor can be seen as playing a role when there is correlation in the data. This role will decrease as the inverse correlation matrix becomes more exact.

It is of interest to investigate the behavior of the matrix estimation error. Consider Eq. (10)

$$E_p(k+1) = \phi(k+1) - \hat{Y}(k+1)V_p(k) \quad (10)$$

This is the equation for all of the error calculations from the first time step to time step $k+1$. By use of the RLS gain equation and Eq. (9), we may write Eq. (11) as shown.

$$E_p(k+1) = E_p(k) - e_p(k)G_p(k)V_p(k-1) - e_p^+(k+1) \quad (11)$$

The sum of the squares of all the output estimation errors may be defined as in Eq. (12).

$$\Sigma_p(k+1) = E_p(k+1)E_p^T(k+1) \quad (12)$$

Using Eq. (11), Eq. (12) may be rewritten as shown in Eq. (13).

$$\Sigma_p(k+1) = \lambda \Sigma_p(k) + e_p^+(k+1) \{ e_p^-(k+1) \}^T \quad (13)$$

Equation (13) is recursive. If the value of the forgetting factor is chosen as one, the sum of the error squares will continue to grow. If the forgetting factor is less than one, old errors will be forgotten as time increases. Equation (13) is a key equation in the derivation of the FTF with forgetting factor.

The derivation of the FTF may be found in Ref. [1]. However, the algorithm must be modified to include a forgetting factor. Consider Eq. (14) shown below.

$$V_{p+1}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} u(0) & u(1) & u(2) & \cdots & u(p+1) & \cdots & u(k+1) \\ y(0) & y(1) & \cdots & y(p) & \cdots & y(k) \\ u(0) & u(1) & \cdots & u(p) & \cdots & u(k) \\ & v(0) & \cdots & v(p-1) & \cdots & v(k-1) \\ & & \ddots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ & & & v(0) & \cdots & v(k-p) \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

The matrix of Eq. (14) is similar to that of Eq. (3), but includes an additional time step. Equation (14) may be partitioned in such a way as to form the forward time step updates and backward time step updates. Equation (15) is the partitioning for the forward updates and differs from Ref. [1] in that it includes a forgetting factor.

$$V_{p+1}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} \phi_{\bar{u}}(-1)\sqrt{\lambda} & \phi_{\bar{u}}(k-1)\sqrt{\lambda} & y_{\bar{u}}(k) \\ 0 & V_p(k-2)\sqrt{\lambda} & v_p(k-1) \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

$$\phi_{\bar{u}}(-1) = \begin{bmatrix} u(0) \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad y_{\bar{u}}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} u(k+1) \\ y(k) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\phi_{\bar{u}}(k-1) = \begin{bmatrix} u(1) & u(2) & u(3) & \cdots & u(p+1) & \cdots & u(k) \\ y(0) & y(1) & y(2) & \cdots & y(p) & \cdots & y(k-1) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$v_p(k-1) = [u(k) \quad v(k-1) \quad \cdots \quad v(k-p)]^T$$

Equation (15) may be used to form the inverse of the data correlation matrix as shown below.

$$P_{p+1}(k) = [V_{p+1}(k)V_{p+1}^T(k)]^{-1} \quad (16)$$

Plugging in Eq. (15) into Eq. (16) and using matrix inverse identities and matrix manipulations, we obtain Eq. (17).

$$P_{p+1}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\Sigma}_p^{-1}(k) & -\bar{\Sigma}_p^{-1}(k)\bar{Y}_p(k) \\ -\bar{Y}_p^T(k)\bar{\Sigma}_p^{-1}(k) & \bar{Y}_p^T(k)\bar{\Sigma}_p^{-1}(k)\bar{Y}_p(k) + P_p(k-1) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\hat{Y}(k) = [\phi_{\bar{u}}(k-1)V_p^T(k-2)\lambda + y_{\bar{u}}(k)v_p^T(k-1)]$$

$$[\phi_{\bar{u}}(k-1)V_p^T(k-2)\lambda + y_{\bar{u}}(k)v_p^T(k-1)]^T \quad (17)$$

$$\bar{\Sigma}_p(k) =$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \phi_{\bar{u}}(k-1) & \hat{Y}_p(k)V_p(k-2) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \phi_{\bar{u}}(k-1) & \hat{Y}_p(k)V_p(k-2) \end{bmatrix}^T \lambda$$

$$+ \begin{bmatrix} y_{\bar{u}}(k) & \hat{Y}_p(k)v_p(k-1) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} y_{\bar{u}}(k-1) & \hat{Y}_p(k)v_p(k-1) \end{bmatrix}^T$$

$$+ \phi_{\bar{u}}(-1)\phi_{\bar{u}}^T(-1)\lambda$$

Similar to Eq. (7), the update equation for the forward time parameters is given in Eq. (18).

$$\hat{Y}(k) = \hat{Y}(k-1) + \bar{e}_p^-(k)G_p(k-1) \quad (18)$$

$$\bar{e}_p^-(k) = y_u(k) - \hat{Y}(k-1)v_p(k-1)$$

$$\bar{e}_p^+(k) = y_u(k) - \hat{Y}(k)v_p(k-1)$$

Here the quantities $\bar{e}_p^-(k)$ and $\bar{e}_p^+(k)$ are the forward error estimates before and after the forward parameters are updated respectively. The gain vector $G_p(k)$ is the same as that of the RLS algorithm. This gain vector may be rewritten as shown in Eq. (19).

$$G_{p+1}(k) = \frac{v_{p+1}^T(k)P_{p+1}(k-1)}{\lambda + v_{p+1}^T(k)P_{p+1}(k-1)v_{p+1}(k)} = v_{p+1}^T(k)P_{p+1}(k) \quad (19)$$

By inserting Eq. (17) into (19) we obtain an equation for the gain update as shown in Eq. (20).

$$G_{p+1}(k) = \left[\begin{array}{c} \bar{e}_p^+(k) \\ \bar{e}_p^-(k) \end{array} \right]^T \bar{\Sigma}_p^{-1}(k) \left[\begin{array}{c} G_p(k-1) \\ \bar{e}_p^+(k) \end{array} \right]^T \bar{\Sigma}_p^{-1}(k) \hat{Y}(k) \quad (20)$$

Equation (20) can be partitioned as shown below.

$$G_{p+1}(k) = \left[\begin{array}{cc} G_{p+1}^r(k) & G_{p+1}^a(k) \end{array} \right]$$

Here, $G_{p+1}^a(k)$ is of dimensions $1 \times (r+m)$ where r is the number of inputs and m the output.

We next define the conversion factor as shown in Eq. (21).

$$\gamma_p(k) = 1 - G_p(k)v_p(k) \quad (21)$$

The conversion factor may be used to express a relationship between the estimation error terms as shown in Eq. (22).

$$\bar{e}_p^+(k) = \gamma_p(k-1)\bar{e}_p^-(k) \quad (22)$$

Equations (22) and (20) may be used to express the conversion factor recursively as shown in Eq. (23).

$$\gamma_{p+1}(k) = \gamma_p(k-1) - \left[\begin{array}{c} \bar{e}_p^+(k) \\ \bar{e}_p^-(k) \end{array} \right]^T \bar{\Sigma}_p^{-1}(k) \bar{e}_p^+(k) \quad (23)$$

Finally, an expression similar to that of Eq. (13) may be used to express the sum of the squares of the estimation errors as shown in Eq. (24).

$$\bar{\Sigma}_p(k+1) = \lambda \bar{\Sigma}_p(k) + \bar{e}_p^+(k+1)\{\bar{e}_p^-(k+1)\}^T \quad (24)$$

The FTF algorithm uses interplay between the forward time estimates and the backward time estimates. Consider the matrix equation (14), which may be partitioned as shown in Eq. (25).

$$V_{p+1}(k) = \left[\begin{array}{cc} \sqrt{\lambda}V_p(k-1) & v_p(k) \\ \sqrt{\lambda}\phi(k-p-1) & y_u(k-p) \end{array} \right] \quad (25)$$

As for the forward time estimator, the inverse correlation matrix may be determined from the Eq. (26) shown below using a matrix inverse identity and matrix manipulations.

$$P_{p+1}(k) = \left[\begin{array}{cc} P_p(k) + \hat{Y}_p^T(k)\bar{\Sigma}_p^{-1}(k)\hat{Y}_p(k) & -\hat{Y}_p^T(k)\bar{\Sigma}_p^{-1}(k) \\ -\bar{\Sigma}_p^{-1}(k)\hat{Y}_p(k) & \bar{\Sigma}_p^{-1}(k) \end{array} \right] \quad (26)$$

The backward time parameters and estimation error squares are defined as shown below.

$$\hat{Y}_p(k) = \phi_u(k-p)V_p^T(k)\left[V_p(k)V_p^T(k)\right]^{-1}$$

$$\bar{\Sigma}_p(k) = \left[\begin{array}{c} \phi_u(k-p) - \hat{Y}(k)V_p(k) \\ \phi_u(k-p) - \hat{Y}(k)V_p(k) \end{array} \right]^T$$

Similar to Eq. (7), a recursive expression for the update of the backward time parameters is shown in Eq. (27).

$$\hat{Y}(k) = \hat{Y}(k-1) + \bar{e}_p^-(k)G_p(k) \quad (27)$$

$$\bar{e}_p^-(k) = y_u(k-p) - \hat{Y}(k-1)v_p(k)$$

The last equality is the backward time estimation error before the backward time parameters are updated. As in Eq. (19), the gain vector may be updated using the backward time variables. This is shown in Eq. (28).

$$G_{p+1}(k) = v_{p+1}^T(k)P_{p+1}(k) \quad (28)$$

$$G_{p+1}(k) = \left[\begin{array}{c} G_p(k) - \left[\begin{array}{c} \bar{e}_p^+(k) \\ \bar{e}_p^-(k) \end{array} \right]^T \bar{\Sigma}_p^{-1}(k) \hat{Y}_p(k) \\ \left[\begin{array}{c} \bar{e}_p^+(k) \\ \bar{e}_p^-(k) \end{array} \right]^T \bar{\Sigma}_p^{-1}(k) \end{array} \right]$$

The backwards time estimation error after the parameters are updated is given by,

$$\bar{e}_p^-(k) = y_u(k-p) - \hat{Y}(k)v_p(k)$$

As for the forward time estimation routine, the gain matrix $G_{p+1}(k)$ is partitioned into $G_{p+1}^r(k)$ and $G_{p+1}^a(k)$ which are the recursive part and augmented part, respectively. This is shown in Eq. (29).

$$G_{p+1}(k) = \left[\begin{array}{cc} G_{p+1}^r(k) & G_{p+1}^a(k) \end{array} \right] \quad (29)$$

The recursive and augmented parts may be expressed as shown in Eq. (30).

$$G_{p+1}^r(k) = \left[1 - \left[\begin{array}{c} \bar{e}_p^+(k) \\ \bar{e}_p^-(k) \end{array} \right]^T \bar{\Sigma}_p^{-1}(k) \bar{e}_p^-(k) \right] G_p(k) - \left[\begin{array}{c} \bar{e}_p^+(k) \\ \bar{e}_p^-(k) \end{array} \right]^T \bar{\Sigma}_p^{-1}(k) \hat{Y}_p(k-1) \quad (30)$$

$$G_{p+1}^a(k) = \left[\begin{array}{c} \bar{e}_p^+(k) \\ \bar{e}_p^-(k) \end{array} \right]^T \bar{\Sigma}_p^{-1}(k)$$

The gain vector $G_{p+1}(k)$ is a common term shared by both the forward and backward time updates. Also shared is the conversion factor as defined for the forward time update. Here, it may be used to interact with the forward time update. As before, the error before and after the backward parameter updates may be related by

$$\bar{e}_p^+(k) = \gamma_p(k)\bar{e}_p^-(k)$$

The above equation may be used to derive Eq. (31) which is a recursive expression for the conversion factor.

$$\gamma_{p+1}(k) = \gamma_p(k) - \left[\begin{array}{c} \bar{e}_p^+(k) \\ \bar{e}_p^-(k) \end{array} \right]^T \bar{\Sigma}_p^{-1}(k) \bar{e}_p^+(k) \quad (31)$$

Equation (31) may be rewritten as shown in Eq. (32).

$$\gamma_p(k) = \frac{\gamma_{p+1}(k)}{1 - G_{p+1}^a(k)\bar{e}_p^-(k)} \quad (32)$$

The FTF algorithm for the SISO case is given below with the forgetting factor included.

Initialization:

$$G_p(k-1) = \left[\begin{array}{cccc} 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \end{array} \right]$$

$$\hat{Y}(k-1) = \left[\begin{array}{cccc} 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \end{array} \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{\Sigma}_p(k-1) &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \\ \gamma_p(k-1) &= 1 \\ \hat{Y}(k-1) &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \end{bmatrix}\end{aligned}$$

Recursive Loop, compute at each time step:

Forward-Time Update:

$$\begin{aligned}v_p(k-1) &= \\ & \begin{bmatrix} u(k) & y(k-1) & u(k-1) & y(k-2) & u(k-2) & \dots \end{bmatrix}^T \\ y_{\bar{u}}(k) &= \begin{bmatrix} u(k+1) & y(k) \end{bmatrix}^T \\ \bar{e}_p^-(k) &= y_{\bar{u}}(k) - \hat{Y}_p(k-1)v_p(k-1) \\ \bar{e}_p^+(k) &= \gamma_p(k-1)\bar{e}_p^-(k) \\ \bar{\Sigma}_p(k) &= \lambda\bar{\Sigma}_p(k-1) + \bar{e}_p^+(k)\bar{e}_p^-(k)^T \\ \hat{Y}_p(k) &= \hat{Y}_p(k-1) + \bar{e}_p^-(k)G_p(k-1) \\ G_{p+1}(k) &= \\ & \begin{bmatrix} \bar{e}_p^-(k)^T \{\bar{\Sigma}_p(k)\}^{-1} & G_p(k-1) - \bar{e}_p^-(k)\{\bar{\Sigma}_p(k)\}^{-1}\hat{Y}_p(k) \end{bmatrix} \\ & \text{Partition as } G_{p+1}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} G_{p+1}^r(k) & G_{p+1}^a(k) \end{bmatrix} \\ \gamma_{p+1}(k) &= \gamma_p(k-1) - \bar{e}_p^+(k)^T \{\bar{\Sigma}_p(k)\}^{-1} \bar{e}_p^+(k)\end{aligned}$$

Backward-Time Update:

$$\begin{aligned}v_p(k) &= \begin{bmatrix} u(k+1) & y(k) & u(k) & y(k-1) & u(k-1) & \dots \end{bmatrix}^T \\ y_u(k-p) &= \begin{bmatrix} y(k+2) & u(k-2) \end{bmatrix}^T \\ \bar{e}_p^-(k) &= y_u(k-p) - \hat{Y}_p(k-1)v_p(k) \\ G_p(k) &= \frac{G_{p+1}^r(k) + G_{p+1}^a(k)\hat{Y}_p(k-1)}{1 - G_{p+1}^a(k)\bar{e}_p^-(k)} \\ \hat{Y}_p(k) &= \hat{Y}_p(k-1) + \bar{e}_p^-(k)G_p(k) \\ \gamma_p(k) &= \frac{\gamma_{p+1}(k)}{1 - G_{p+1}^a(k)\bar{e}_p^-(k)}\end{aligned}$$

2.) Simulations:

This section presents simulations for the RLS and FTF with forgetting factors. The algorithms are applied to a SISO second order system with a lightly damped pole. A comparison is made between the adaptation rates and number of operations for each algorithm. The transfer function of the second order system to be initially identified is given below.

$$\begin{aligned}\text{num} &= 1 + 0.9z^{-1} + 0.8z^{-2} \quad \text{den} = 1 - 2r\cos(w)z^{-1} + r^2z^{-2} \\ r &= 0.9 \quad w = 0.3\pi\end{aligned}$$

Where den is the denominator, num is the numerator, r is one minus the damping, and w is the resonant frequency. The identification takes place between time steps zero to one thousand. At k=1000, the damping and natural frequency are instantaneously changed to that given below and the ability of the identification routines to track the

changes is observed along with the number of floating point operations for each time step.

$$r = 0.98 \quad w = 0.1\pi$$

Figure 1 shows the tracking error of the RLS, dotted line, compared to the tracking error of the FTF, solid line, with a forgetting factor of 0.97.

Figure 1. Plot of RLS tracking error, dashed, versus FTF tracking error, solid.

In Fig. 1, we see that for the same forgetting factor the FTF tracked the system change faster than the RLS algorithm. For both cases, the input was normally distributed noise with a variance of one and the same seed was used to initiate both random sequences. It is to be noted, however, that the RLS tracking error never exceeded an absolute value of eight while the magnitude of the FTF error went up to fifty. This faster tracking and larger instantaneous error may be due to the fact that the FTF uses the energy in the error, i.e., error squared, rather than the error as the RLS does.

In Fig. 2 we see a timing comparison between the RLS and the FTF algorithms. While the time in milliseconds is a function of the machine the code is run on, the two can be compared together since they were run on the same machine. As can be seen from the plots, the algorithms take about the same amount of time to identify a 16th order system. For lower orders the RLS ran faster. However, for higher orders the FTF performed faster. As can be seen the time saved by using the FTF for large order system is considerable.

Figure 2. Timing for RLS, dashed line, and FTF, solid line

3.) Use of FTF in Feedback Control:

The forward time parameters may be used as the parameters for feedback control. Consider Eq. (33) that uses the forward parameters to produce estimates of the plant output and a prediction of the future input.

$$\hat{y}_u(k) = \begin{bmatrix} u(k+1) \\ y(k) \end{bmatrix} = \hat{Y}_p(k-1)v_p(k-1) \quad (33)$$

Here we have a prediction of the future control input needed to drive a plant to a known state. If the desired plant output $R(k)$ is known and the forward parameters have converged, then Eq. (33) may be written to track a desired reference as in Eq. (34).

$$u(k+2) = Y_u \tilde{v}_p(k) \quad (34)$$

In Eq. (34) Y_u is the first row of \hat{Y}_p and $\tilde{v}_p(k)$ is the same as $v_p(k)$ except $y(k)$ has been replaced by the reference $R(k)$. Figure (3) shows the improved performance in the plant given in the simulation section of this paper. The first 500 time steps are used by the FTF to compute the system identification, after which the FTF is switched off and the feedback controller is implemented. The dotted line is the plant response to a unity amplitude square wave and the solid line is the same response with the controller in place. As can be seen in the figure, the forward parameters generated by the FTF may be used as an adaptive predictive feedback controller, see reference [2].

Figure 3. FTF as a Feedback Controller

4.) Experimental Results:

This section presents the experimental results of applying the FTF to flight data obtained from an Aligned Signal Flight Control Computer (FCC) flying B737 software. The area of flight used was from glide slope engaged to flare and the commands of interest are the throttle and the elevator. The flight conditions are ideal with no winds, gust, or RF present. Sensor data coming into the FCC was recorded along with the throttle and elevator commands. The recorded data was then passed through the FTF in order to determine the transfer function from sensor inputs to command outputs. Figure 4 shows the setup. The FCC is placed into the High Intensity Radiated Field (HIRF) chamber and ran closed loop with the B737 simulator.

Figure 4. Experimental Setup

Figure 5 is a plot of the throttle error. This error is the residual, which is the difference between the one step prediction and the actual measurement of the command. Figure 6 is a plot of the estimated coefficients of the throttle

transfer function. Figures 7 and 8 are the tracking error and the parameters of the elevator respectively.

Figure 5: Plot of Throttle Tracking Error

Figure 6: Throttle Parameters

Figure 7: Plot of Elevator Tracking Error

Figure 8: Elevator Parameters

By examining Figure 4-7, it is seen that the FTF tracks the commands in a reasonable fashion. The figures shown here represent data taken before glide slop was engaged and after flare has occurred, therefore several mode switches can be seen in the data. These transitions create a rise in the tracking error and a change in the plotted coefficients as can be seen in the figures.

5.) Conclusion

The FTF offers another way to perform real-time system identification and error tracking. The contribution of this paper is the inclusion of a forgetting factor in the FTF algorithm. The forgetting factor allows real time tracking of changes in a system without the need to restart the identification processes. As demonstrated, the FTF may be used to monitor the changes in a FCC. This is advantageous when applied to the fault detection problem in that the FTF may be used to detect changes in a flight critical system due to hard and/or soft failures. Future work will include use of the FTF in real time fault detection problems. The FTF has the advantage of being less computationally intensive than traditional system identification techniques resulting in increased bandwidth.

References:

- 1.) Applied System Identification, Jer-nan Juang, Prentice Hall, 1994.
- 2.) Identification and Control of Mechanical Systems, Jer-nan Juang & Minh Q. Phan, Cambridge, 2001